

PROBLEMS RELATED TO THE VIRTUAL EDUCATION IN PERIODS OF PANDEMIA IN STUDENTS AND EDUCATIONAL

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the problems of Virtual education in the same way, specifies the role and importance of information and communication technologies (ICT) in this educational modality. In the same way the role of the teacher and the students and the level of communication between teacher and student greatly influences the development of Virtual sessions. Similarly, the deficiencies in the use of ICT by the student and the teacher can cause frustration and serious problems in the performance of their activity. The methodology of Virtual education have characteristics that make it provide advantages in the teaching-learning process. The differences between the methodology of traditional and Virtual education, make that in some many the projects fail because teachers and students do not know the use of ICT under continuous training is necessary. When information and communication technologies (ICT) Plough applied, their potential transforms teaching and learning environments, which allows the creation of virtual learning environments, with non-traditional methodological approaches that moves from individual to collaborative learning, and from transmission to the construction of knowledge. In these environments the role of the teacher is decisive for the success of the student-centered training activity.

Keywords: Use of ICT, motivation and interest, level of communication, the role of the teacher.

INTRODUCTION

In the last times, the societies have changed of form precipitated. In fact, theorists like Harnad consider that the history of the humanity is in dependency of the technological evolution, what has given place to radical changes in the organization of the knowledge and human understanding. In this context, the access to Internet has allowed to elevate the quality of life and the prosperity of the countries(1). Thus it warns that his use is indispensable to favor the communication, the learning and the

culture, motivating that the citizens are better prepared and are more competitive (2). This year 2020 the world confronts to the COVID-19, and to measure that advances by all the planet, the greater part of the countries decided to close temporarily the educational institutions, what affected roughly to the 91 % of the students to world-wide level and for the month of April, around 1600 million boys and youngsters were out of the school (UN 2020). In Peru, as in the majority of countries of the world, opted by the suspension of the face-to-face

educational service, to end to avoid that the educational institutions are sources of contagion between the students. Like this, the only available option was the virtual education(3).

The virtual education allows greater flexibilization regarding the handle of the times, spaces, distances, and offers greater and better opportunities of learning to the educational institutions(4). However, it needs conditions of stick digital, that involve the capacity of connection of students and educational, among other shots. These last conditions generate inequalities in the access to the virtual education by the lack of infrastructure and the fault of training in the students (5). By the previous considerations, proposed like aim: analyze the problems of the virtual education, being one of them the use of the Technologies of the Information and the Communication (TIC)(6), involves to the students joining his interest and his intellectual attention, academic, and also emotional. What has carried to the education to a continuous qualification for the virtualization inside of a modality of learning in which the student has to be more active and cooperative in the process (7) like this like the educational that is forced to use virtual tools although it result him difficult, knowing that they exist multiple personal problems that prevent the development or the progress of the virtual education, in the different professional careers the challenge of the students is to keep in this situation of abandonment by the Peruvian State in what it refers to subjects of upper education, the

desertion of the students of the public and private universities has been of 30% (8).

In this sense, the academic field requires of new methods, a permanent dialogue and links in search of points of intersection especially in the personal development of the students and his links with the technologies of the information putting emphasis in the importance of an education that promote the tolerance, the creativity, the cooperation, the reflection and the culture. These are the essential elements of a model of university education strengthened by the capacity of investigation and of innovation.

Methodology

Design of the study

This investigation, is of descriptive and explanatory character, is a study on the problems in the virtual education in periods of pandemic in educational and students. The methodological proposal designed from an explanatory perspective and applied the instrument of the survey (9), headed to students and educational of the career of infirmary. The survey had answers of 279 students and 7 educational. The surveys developed between March and April of 2021.

Selection of the sample

The sample invited, being the group of elements of the population to which asks that they participate in the investigation, corresponds to students and educational, establishing a simple random sample (10), the study

considered the virtual survey like optimum methodological mechanism to collect information, and headed to students of different semesters of the career of infirmity. The percentage analyzed considers significant inside the universe and in this sense the sample allows to infer precise results.

The study adopted a methodology from the technical survey being the instrument a questionnaire, of quantitative type. The survey has designed with enclosed questions of nominal and ordinal scale, has based in a simple random sampling (11). The statistical analysis employee on the survey has been the descriptive analysis based in frequencies and percentages by means of the proof of chi-square. Besides, the methodological proposal includes questions with multiple alternative for the most defined subjects on the experience, qualification of the TIC and the motivation, condition, role and physical and mental wear of the educational and students, in this way, have combined questions of identification, of intention, of information and of opinion.

Context of the study

The main variables of the questionnaires were: to) Diagnose the qualification and experience in the TIC(12); b) Diagnose the level of interest and condition more important in educational and students; and (13) c) Analysis and diagnostic of the role, motivation of the educational and students (14);d)Diagnose the physical and mental wear of the educational and students. This instrument was validated

by a signpost of experts (n=2) in matter of communication and education before being implemented resulted the reliability of the instrument of the 0.89 according to alpha of Cronbach. Later it made an electronic version of the survey that was sent to forty students of the X semester and 4 educational. So much the students like the educational participants were informed of the study and his consent was requested to participate in the same. To take the survey took in account the following headings: • For the students and educational: qualification and experience in the tools of the TIC in the virtual education during the pandemic and diagnostic of motivation, interest, physical wear, condition and role more important of the student and educational university. In both surveys, for the collected of data used enclosed questions of nominal and ordinal scales. They included enclosed questions for the most defined subjects on the qualification and experience of the TIC. The problems to consider are 7, analyzed and identified from the practice of the virtual classrooms, of agreement to some scopes done by the students and educational, of agreement to the conjuncture current. The statistical analysis employee in the surveys was descriptive, based in frequencies and percentages, whose answers will instrument in percentages. The internal consistency of the test presented a reliability with a 0.89 of Alpha of Cronbach by means of the proof of chi-square(15), confirming measure the construct of the multiple factors , when the coefficient of Alpha is $>.90$, will be able to say that the reliability of the instrument is excellent

and if >it is ,80 will say that it is good. The questionnaire sent through the application of Google Form of the same way the consent informed.

SEVEN PROBLEMS IN THE VIRTUAL EDUCATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL And STUDENTS IN PERIODS OF PANDEMIA

RESULTS And DISCUSSION

Importance of the qualification in the use of the virtual tools

The results like empirical evidences expressed in the table 1, answer to the interrogate formulated: You in his

condition of student and educational university considers important the qualification in the use of the virtual tools? Considering the participation of students and educational of the career of infirmary those that refer that it is not so important 35.84%(students) and very important 71%(educational). However, considering the participation only of students of the career of infirmary that root in the provinces and districts of Puno, according to the results the greater percentage considers a problem since it is of great importance the qualification in the use of the virtual tools more still in this period of pandemic of the COVID 19.

TABLE 1
Importance of the qualification in the use of the virtual tools

It is important the qualification in the use of the virtual tools:	STUDENTS		EDUCATIONAL	
	fi	hi%	fi	hi%
AT ALL IMPORTANT	10	3.58%	2	0%
LITTLE IMPORTANT	31	11.11%	0	0%
NO SO IMPORTANT	100	35.84%	0	0%
IMPORTANT	78	27.96%	0	29%
VERY IMPORTANT	60	21.51%	5	71%
TOTAL	279	100.00%	7	100%

SOURCE: Questionnaire

The digital and virtual resources have purchased a fundamental importance in the current context and have established like essential elements of the society, no longer only like facilitators of the

communication and of the interpersonal relations, but also like key factors in the training of the individual (16) . Thus, the previous results evidencing that the educational considers very important

the qualification in the use of the virtual tools because, goes purchasing more consciousness on the utility of the virtual and digital commands for academic ends, leaving to use them like mere instruments of entertainment or socialization to begin to use them like educational tools (Bonilla-of the-River, Diego-Mantecón and Lena-Acebo, 2018)(17). For this was necessary to contrast the following statistical hypothesis:

The results resemble an article published by the “Universidad Tecnológica de Peru” where mention: “that qualify to the personnel, so much of individual form like group, has to be part of the priorities of the business strategy, during this situation and in the future immediate ”(18). The“ forced isolation ”that has lived good part of the world during the last months, has generated conditions more adapted for the qualification for the work. This is due to that they suppress, for example, time of transfer and long stays in educational institutions, what translates in decrease of the labor stress (19). It could consider that to qualify in this conjuncture only requires of time, will and proof. The importance of the qualification in the middle of the pandemic has to see no only with the virtual courses, but also with the webinars or the masterclasses dictated by important academic referents.

Of the same way, Vinicio Chávez ensures: *“The utilization of the platforms generalized in the Universities, however, this educational*

alternative does not advance positively had to fundamentally to the scarce pedagogical preparation, what goes to the detriment of an autonomous training, independent and flexible own of a significant learning by part of the student body”(18). What does us affirm that without qualification there will be a good education and learning already was by factor time or economic.

On the other hand, Víctor Barrier affirms that: *“The importance that owe to have the virtual qualification so that they keep on being a contribution of big value for the educational, transforming in a resource dynamized, able to improve and improve the cognitive levels of the student by means of the different applications of the use and taste of the students, promoting the critical thought and the capital of the knowledge”* (19). Of this way coincide in the importance of the qualification that owe to have the educational and students before, during and after the virtual sessions.

EXPERIENCE WITH THE USE OF THE TIC

When it pretends appreciate the table 2, the experience with the handle of the TIC, the investigation remits to the following question: You has experience with the use of the TIC? The students of the university answered in 32.26% (90 students) that had experience in course workshop, followed of 27.24% (76 students) of students that answered to do a course of handle of TIC and 40.50% (113 students) answered that they followed another course in the

TIC. Whereas the educational answered in greater percentage, that the experience in the use of the TIC like applications of academic character had it in diplomats or workshops reaching

57% (4 educational), instead 43% (3 educational) answered that had experience in other courses.

TABLE 2
Experience with the use of the TIC

Had experience in the use of the TIC:	STUDENTS		EDUCATIONAL	
	fi	hi%	fi	hi%
ANOTHER COURSE	10	3.58%	4	57%
SECOND ESP	25	8.96%	0	0%
COURSE - WORKSHOP	78	27.96%	4	0%
UNIVERSITY WORKSHOP	90	32.26%	3	43%
COURSE	76	27.24%	0	0
TOTAL	279	100.00%	7	100%

SOURCE: Questionnaire

The results obtained approach to the reality of some authors like Maria Requeyra in his article mentions that: *“the TIC are processes that have transformed the current society, with his incorporation so much in the economic field, social and labor as in the educational fields, familiar and personal, what has generated new social interactions and a gap between the population that has access to the technology and the one who does not have it, situation that has hit fundamentally the educational field, where have gone incorporating the TIC of progressive way, with some reservations so much of the educational*

population as of the student population” (20). Of the same way the students do not have a lot of experience in the use of the TIC and the educational have experience with the use of the TIC.

On the other hand Romina Cariaga, in his article mentions: *“The experiences with TIC have been very diverse, in some relates observes the footprint of the experience in the pedagogical knowledge built. In others, warns that the subject has suffered the experience and has hampered his transformation”*(2). Of this way the use of the TIC has hampered the learning in the students with the courses that carried had experience in the use of the

virtual platforms what is not sufficient without the daily practice for the correct use of the TIC.

ROLE OF THE EDUCATIONAL And STUDENTS IN THE VIRTUAL CLASSROOMS

The educational exert an important role protagonist in the transition of the face-to-face education to the virtual, of this way the feedback has been fundamental for the educational in 29% and for the students 6.81%. The student considers of majority form that keep

communication with his educational is fundamental for the good development of the virtual classes in 30.47% and the educational 71%. Nevertheless, the students recognize some deficiencies that focalizing preferably in the confidence with the educational in 4.30%. On the other hand, only 37.63% of students consider that the motivation is a role of the educational that are appearances little characteristic inside the virtual educational role.

TABLE 3
Main role of the educational and students

Which considers his/her more important role in in the virtual classroom:	STUDENTS		EDUCATIONAL	
	fi	hi%	fi	hi%
CONFIDENCE	12	4.30%	0	0%
FEEDBACK	19	6.81%	2	29%
THAT THE EDUCATIONAL ANSWER To THE QUESTIONS	58	20.79%	0	0%
COMMUNICATION	85	30.47%	5	71%
MOTIVATION	105	37.63%	0	0%
TOTAL	279	100.00%	7	100.00%

Source: Questionnaire

According to our results do reference to Goddess Perez that mentions: *“The educational virtual has to adjust to the profile of each student because each student imposes his own rhythm of learning.”* Of this way the educational virtual have communication with his students being for them one of the most

important roles and for the students the motivation that will influence in the learning of the students. In reference to the students Perez mentions: *“The role of the student turns into more active and vital for his same process of learning, since it happens to be a receptor of information (of agreement to the*

traditional method of education) to a researcher and administrator of the information that achieves to apprehend the subject of the course. (21) This generates a big responsibility, since it no longer is the educational the one who establishes the limits of information that processes in each unit and for each examination but is he same the one who will do it.

On the other hand, Paulsen affirms: *“The role of the educational centers fundamentally in the dynamization of the group and in assuming functions of organization of the activities, of motivation and creation of a pleasant climate of learning and facilitator educational, providing experiences for the car-learning and the construction of the knowledge”*(22). The functions organize in relations between educational and student, the groups, specific preparation of the educational, control of the information and knowledges, and evaluation. These keep active the communication, basic appearance for the construction of the knowledge. In general terms, in some

surroundings of constructivist learning, a good educational motivates to the students analyzing his representations, giving answers and councils on the representations and especially how learn to make them, as well as stimulate the reflection and the articulation on the learnt (23)

LEVEL OF MOTIVATION IN STUDENTS And EDUCATIONAL

The universities have had to face up of form precipitated to a crisis that has affected forcefully to the university management. In this sense, the level of motivation of the educational in the virtual classrooms has been slightly motivate (43%), much more motivate (14%), less motivate (29%). In this regard the students think of the motivation of the educational to them in the virtual classrooms very motivate (34.41%), slightly motivate (32.62%), some students feel less motivated (17.56%), what does us reflexional in giving theories in the virtual classrooms.

TABLE 4

Level of motivation of the educational and students in the virtual classrooms

You are motivated in the virtual classrooms:	STUDENTS		EDUCATIONAL	
	fi	hi%	fi	hi%
NEVER	16	5.73%	0	0%
NO SO MOTIVANTE	27	9.68%	1	14%
LESS MOTIVANTE	49	17.56%	2	29%

SLIGHTLY MOTIVANTE	91	32.62%	3	43%
MUCH MORE MOTIVANTE	96	34.41%	1	14%
TOTAL	279	100.00%	7	100%

Source: Questionnaire

When speaking of motivation in the virtual classrooms by part of the educational and students pose us this question mark: you is motivated during the sessions of virtual education? The students and educational indicate that the motivation is fundamental part in the sessions of learning.

In this regard Myriam Lancheros mentions that: *“The successes of culmination in any program of virtual training contribute persuasively to the academic agents, generating motivational strategies for the people that wish incursionary in said modality of learning”*(24). Coinciding with our answers of the students and educational the educational shows and keeps motivated to the student in the virtual classrooms the student in this stage of learning with the changes and the stress that contracts to be still in the virtual classrooms the be motivated is important to culminate his studies.

Of the same way Wilimam Zambrano mentions that: *“The student happened to be a passive receptor of knowledges to be active part of his learning, based in his self-esteem, motivation, discipline and confidence, whereas the educational turned into a facilitator of the learning, leaving the traditional*

model and transmission of knowledges, to center in the creation of stages in which the student find and generate conditions to grow in his integral training” (25). Of this way the new approach of virtual education bases in the motivation that gives the educational virtual to his students in the virtual sessions, in such a way that each student see the importance to assist to each session without need to put excuses of schedules or work, where sees the responsibility of the student as it was motivated by the educational.

LEVEL OF PHYSICAL And MENTAL WEAR IN STUDENTS And EDUCATIONAL

The educational and students have exerted a paper protagonist in the transition of the face-to-face education to the virtual. However, in a lot of cases, this traffic has made of form precipitated. In such a way that the work is more arduous when preparing sessions of classes since the physical and mental wear gives always (71.4%) and frequently (29%) for the educational; what does to suppose that for a greater learning of the students the educational has to to use more than 2 virtual tools to be more comprehensible the virtual session. In the case of the students the physical and mental wear

gives always (52.23%) and almost always (25.45%), of this way the students when having greater quantity of works, practical described

overwhelm and do not reach to conclude the works and go up them of suitable way in the virtual platform.

Table 5

Level of physical and mental wear of the educational and students

	STUDENTS		EDUCATIONAL	
	fi	hi%	fi	hi%
You have physical and mental wear in the virtual classes:				
NEVER	12	4.30%	0	0%
HARDLY EVER	15	5.38%	0	0%
FREQUENTLY	35	12.54%	2	29%
ALMOST ALWAYS	71	25.45%	5	71%
ALWAYS	146	52.23%	0	0%
TOTAL	279	99.90%	5	100%

Source: Questionnaire

Of the same way Marco Lovon, mentions that: *“The main consequence is the stress owing to overloads it academic, and apart from the stress, the frustration and the university desertion”*(26) regarding students. The fault of adaptation to the virtual systems is the main problem of the students, also the big quantity of doubts related with the works commissioned, the fault of attention in the virtual sessions by the little connectivity or fail in the internet are technical appearances that repercussion in the learning of the student. What does that have wear physical and mental.

Carmen Diaz, found that 83.5% presents fatigue and fault of energy for

the development of the virtual classes (27) what resembles in our results the students with the mental wear.

Laura Golds et al, coincide with our results. *“Stressors: the surroundings of work and overloads it labor, the employment of new technologies, the uncertainty by the length and consequences of the pandemic, the appearance organizational of the educational institution, and the relations with the surroundings of the student, the conflict and the ambiguity of role”*(28), observes that the factors stressors and the symptoms psychophysics of stress cause physical and mental wear in educational.

LEVEL OF INTEREST IN THE VIRTUAL CLASSROOMS

The negative consequences that the students present in this change of the teaching center in the increase of the load of work, beside the loss of face-to-face contact with the educational and with the mates, being one of the most negative elements, occupying between

all the stages, the first or second position of importance. In this case we speak of the level of interest of the students gives almost always (39.78%) in the virtual sessions and never (3.23%). In the case of the educational the level of interest gives always (57%) and hardly ever (14%).

Table 6

Level of interest in the virtual classrooms of the educational and students:

	STUDENTS		EDUCATIONAL	
	fi	hi%	fi	hi%
You keeps the interest in the virtual classes.				
NEVER	9	3.23%	0	0%
HARDLY EVER	17	6.09%	1	14%
FREQUENTLY	54	19.35%	0	0%
ALMOST ALWAYS	111	39.78%	2	29%
ALWAYS	88	32.54%	4	57%
TOTAL	279	100.00%	6	100%

Source: Questionnaire

The table 6 reflects the answers of the question mark: you keeps interest in the virtual sessions?, that goes from never until always according to our results the students keep interest almost always and the educational keep interest in the virtual classrooms always.

Some authors like María Vera, mentions that: the factors that affect the design of education, and that are related, fundamentally, with the motivation and interest of the apprentices, the theories

of the learning and the didactic methodology, the planning of the virtual course, the control of the learning, the instructiveness and the adaptability of the virtual surroundings of learning (29) Of this way check that the students will have interest in the virtual classrooms if the educational has good strategies of education, beside the tools that the use and that it was profitable so much for the student as for the educational.

On the other hand, Maria Camacho, mentions that: For the implementation

of the educational best practices in the virtual classrooms, requires the suitable pedagogical mediation for the integration of resources, activities and educational evaluations chords to the type of formative process, so that the student purchase the skills that requires the society of the knowledge and the information (30). Of this way coincide in the interest that keeps the student in the sessions of learning by the motivation of the educational and the pedagogy and strategies of learning that use for the good development of the virtual sessions.

THE MOST IMPORTANT CONDITION OF THE STUDENT And EDUCATIONAL

The most important condition in the students and educational during the

development of the virtual sessions, obeys to the following question mark: which is the most important condition of you in the virtual classroom? The students answered that have of time is the most important condition (44.80%), since the pandemic has made possible that the students distribute his time in the studies and the work and being personal of health hampers them assist to the virtual classrooms also influences the access to the technology of internet to develop the sessions of virtual education whereas, the educational answered that the most important condition is to dominate the TIC (86%) in such a way that they when being qualified keep the pedagogical strategies, have the sufficient capacity of coverage and supportability to develop sessions of virtual education .

Table 7

Condition more important of the educational and student in the development of the virtual classrooms

	STUDENTS		EDUCATIONAL	
	fi	hi%	fi	hi%
Which is the most important condition of you in the virtual classroom.				
BE RESPONSIBLE	12	4.30%	0	0%
HAVE MATERIAL OF SUPPORT	17	6.09%	1	14%
DOMINATE THE TIC	43	15.41%	6	86%
BE CONNECTED OF CONTINUOUS WAY	82	29.39%	0	0%
HAVE OF TIME	125	44.80%	0	0%
TOTAL	279	100.00%	0	0%

Source: Questionnaire

In this table resume the condition of the student and educational in the virtual classroom. Some authors like Mireya Squirrel mentions in his article: *Like general conclusion, the quality of the teaching in virtual environments articulates in function of the integral knowledge that possess the educational around the pedagogies and didactic of avant-garde of face to the technological developments* (31). Of this way contrast our results with the command of the TIC in the virtual classrooms by part of the educational of the university, this involves the good learning of the students in the process of education.

Paul Rugeles, mentions: “The enhancing factors for the configuration of the students in the virtual half are the experiences, like the self-discipline, the self-learning, the critical and reflexive

analysis, and the work collaborative” (32). They are varied the appearances that have come evolving along the time in relation to pedagogical practices and the way to understand the relation between education and learning. Likewise, in the actuality pretends change the emphasis of the pedagogy centered in the education to a pedagogy centered in the learning, so that of this way the students adopt a more active position in front of his own processes of learning and favor the autonomous learning, looking for that the students learn to learn. These changes of paradigm in matter of education have to happen of the pedagogies centered in the education, to happen to pedagogies centered in the learning, giving place to a more active role of the students and educational.

CONTRASTING OF HYPOTHESIS

7 PROBLEMS	STUDENTS And EDUCATIONAL	CHI CALCULATE D CHI CRITICISES	CON FIAB ILID AD	SIG NIF ICA NCI A	FREQ UENC Y EXPE CTED	
CAPACITAC ION OF THE TIC	<i>No so important</i>	35.84 %	X ² criticism= 9.49	95%	5%	55.8
	<i>Very important</i>	71%	X ² calculated= 92.77 P= <0.05			
EXPERIENC E IN THE TIC	Workshop	32.26 %	X ² criticism= 9.49	95%	5%	55.8
	Other courses	57%	X ² calculated= 91.70 P= <0.05			
ROLE IN THE CLASSROOM	Motivation	37.63 %	X ² criticism= 9.49	95%	5%	55.8
	Communication with the	71%	X ² calculated=			

MS VITUALES	student		117.40			
				P= <0.05		
LEVEL OF MOTIVACION	Very motivante	34.41 %	X ² criticism= 9.49	95%	5%	55.8
	Slightly motivante	43%	X ² calculated= 95.25			
LEVEL OF WEAR FISICO And MENTAL	Always	52.23 %	X ² criticism= 9.49	95%	5%	55.8
	Almost always	71%	X ² calculated= 221.91			
LEVEL OF INTERES	Almost always	39.53 %	X ² criticism= 9.49	95%	5%	55.8
	Always	57%	X ² calculated= 139.48			
CONDITION MORE IMPORTANT	Have of time	44.80 %	X ² criticism= 9.49	95%	5%	55.8
	Dominate the TIC	86%	X ² calculated = 162.42			
			P = <0.05			

When doing the contrasting of hypothesis of the 7 problems found in students and educational has arrived to the conclusion to accept the alternating hypotheses. Like chi- calculated is greater to the chi- critical or tabulated, then Refuses the Invalid Hypothesis (Ho) and accepts the alternating Hypothesis, for 95% of the level of confidence, that is to say that, the chi – calculated is greater to the chi-critical or tabulated this indicates us that the value of P is lower to 5%, then the differences in the frequencies observed between the 5 alternatives are statistically significant.

- H1: The level of qualification is very important in the

educational and no so important in the students. For 95% of the level of confidence.

- H2: The level of experience with the use of the TIC is good for the educational and deficient for the students.
- H3: The level of communication is the main role of the educational and the motivation for students
- H4: The level of motivation is good for the educational and very good for the students
- H5: The level of the physical and mental wear is very extenuate for the educational and students

- H6: The level of interest in the virtual classrooms is always for the educational and almost always for the students
- H7: The most important condition of the educational in the virtual classroom is to dominate the virtual tools and for the students is to have of time.

CONCLUSIONS

What lives at present with the use of the TIC, has generated changes in the process of education-learning, when including these tools like part of the technological pedagogy in the virtual modality. In the educational institutions see a series of problems regarding the use of the virtual tools in students and educational. This article bases in the description of the problems found in the students and educational. The strategies of the educational are distinct, depending of the type of technology with which explain, and of the type of culture organizational that possess. The TIC designate, to his time, a group of innovations in the use of tools that allow a redesign of the operation of the society. What guarantees a real exploitation in the learning of the students and the education of the educational is the good use of TIC so that the contents are produced, transmitted and perceived by the students. The very used TIC can generate new opportunities of access to the information, create capacities, improve the education and learning, promote the development and, in definite, allow to advance in the virtual education. Regarding the role of the

students and educational, it is necessary to consider that the motivation is fundamental for the students and the communication for the educational this would have to be bidirectional, multidirectional, is the integration of several means in one (digital and technological platforms), the motivation is important part in the development of the education synchrony and asynchrony like part of the methodology complement with virtual spaces, by means of the networks. Regarding the physical and mental wear in the virtual education sees extenuate in students and educational by the quantity of virtual works and the preparation of classes with the virtual tools what contracts a time for the fulfillment of the aims of education learning. The technologies are a half, no an end in himself same. For the development of the virtual education, has to consider : time, place, space, interaction, technology and self-supervision that forms part of the interest and condition of the student, to develop the sessions the educational has command of the TIC like his fundamental role in the pedagogy of this way the student almost always is motivated in this modality, looks for the place and the most timely space and adapted to his own reality, to make his activities of learning and interactor with the educational, mates and material, the times that he wish, for which use the TIC that are to his scope, and establishes his own control.

Thankfulness

To the Private University San Carlos for making possible the development of this investigation, to the and the educational

colleagues and students of the career of nursing, especially to the team of investigation that accompanied us with actions in the investigation.

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